

A New Graphical Password: Combination of Recall & Recognition based Approach

Authors : Md. Asraful Haque, Babbar Imam

Abstract : Information Security is the most describing problem in present times. To cop up with the security of the information, the passwords were introduced. The alphanumeric passwords are the most popular authentication method and still used up to now. However, text based passwords suffer from various drawbacks such as they are easy to crack through dictionary attacks, brute force attacks, keylogger, social engineering etc. Graphical Password is a good replacement for text password. Psychological studies say that human can remember pictures better than text. So this is the fact that graphical passwords are easy to remember. But at the same time due to this reason most of the graphical passwords are prone to shoulder surfing. In this paper, we have suggested a shoulder-surfing resistant graphical password authentication method. The system is a combination of recognition and pure recall based techniques. Proposed scheme can be useful for smart hand held devices (like smart phones i.e. PDAs, ipod, iphone, etc) which are more handy and convenient to use than traditional desktop computer systems.

Keywords : Authentication, Graphical Password, Text Password, Information Security, Shoulder-surfing.

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